

Parental Attitudes Towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education: Barriers and Opportunities for Implementation in Zambian Schools

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Abstract:

Overview: Parental attitudes towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools present a complex landscape of both barriers and opportunities for its implementation. Hence, this study was conducted to analyze parental attitudes towards comprehensive sexuality education within Zambian schools.

Body of Knowledge: Parental attitudes towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools play a critical role in shaping the success and acceptance of such programs. Many parents express concerns about the content and timing of CSE, fearing that it may expose children to sexual information prematurely or contradict cultural and religious values. These concerns often stem from a lack of understanding of the curriculum and a fear that CSE might encourage early sexual experimentation among young people.

Methods: The study adopted a mixed methods approach which is a combination of quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive understanding. The study was conducted in 6 selected schools; 3 secondary and 3 primary schools within Lusaka district in Zambia with a sample of 200 respondents. The population for the study included; Head Teachers, Teachers, Pupils and Parents. Structured open-ended interviews and questionnaires were used to respondents to collect data. The study analyzed data using appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) and Microsoft excel. For the qualitative data, analysis was done based on the research themes.

Results: The findings revealed that many parents express concerns about the appropriateness of CSE, fearing it may encourage premature sexual activity among youths. Cultural and religious beliefs play a significant role in shaping these attitudes, leading to resistance against its implementation. Furthermore, emphasizing the role of CSE in promoting informed and responsible decision-making, preventing teenage pregnancies, and reducing the spread of sexually transmitted infections can further enhance parental support.

Recommendation: By creating an inclusive dialogue that respects cultural sensitivities while advocating for the health and well-being of students, the implementation of CSE in Zambian schools can be more widely accepted and effective.

Keywords: Attitude, Barriers, Beliefs, CSE, and Implementation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) is an inclusive, age-appropriate educational framework designed to provide students with knowledge and skills about sexuality, sexual health, relationships, and personal development. It goes beyond basic sex education by addressing a broad range of topics, including human rights, gender equality, consent, emotional and social aspects of sexuality, and the impact of societal norms and values (Sarah, 2014). CSE aims to equip students with accurate information and critical thinking skills to make informed decisions about their sexual health and relationships. It promotes respect for diversity, fosters positive attitudes towards sexual health, and empowers individuals to advocate for their rights and well-being. By addressing both biological and socio-cultural dimensions, CSE supports the development of healthy, respectful, and consensual relationships and helps to build a foundation for lifelong learning about sexuality and health (Chanda et al, 2024).

Parental attitudes towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools present both barriers and opportunities for its implementation. Mulenga & Penda (2024)'s study noted that many parents in Zambia express concerns about CSE, fearing it might encourage early sexual activity or conflict with cultural and religious values. These reservations often stem from limited understanding or misinformation about the content and goals of CSE. As a result, there is resistance to its inclusion in school curricula, which can hinder its effective implementation. However, there are opportunities to address these barriers through community engagement, awareness campaigns, and sensitization programs that educate parents on the importance of CSE in equipping students with the knowledge and skills to make informed decisions. By involving parents in the development and delivery of CSE programs and addressing their concerns, schools can foster a supportive environment for its successful implementation (Mumba et al, 2019). This collaborative approach can help align educational objectives with parental expectations, ultimately enhancing the acceptance and effectiveness of CSE in Zambian schools.

Parental attitudes towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools are often characterized by a mix of apprehension and cautious acceptance. Many parents express concern that CSE might expose children to information they perceive as inappropriate for their age, fearing it could encourage early sexual activity (MoE, 2013). Cultural and religious beliefs play a significant role in shaping these attitudes, with some parents viewing CSE as conflicting with traditional values. However, there is also a growing recognition of the importance of equipping young people with accurate information to make informed decisions about their sexual health. Opportunities for implementation lie in increasing parental awareness and involvement in CSE programs, ensuring that content is culturally sensitive and aligned with the values of the community (Sekelani, 2021). Effective communication between schools and parents can help address misconceptions and build a collaborative approach to CSE, ultimately fostering a supportive environment for its successful integration into the education system.

Cultural and religious beliefs towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) are deeply rooted perspectives that shape how communities perceive and accept this form of education.

Cultural beliefs often stem from traditional norms and values that dictate appropriate behavior and knowledge about sexuality, which can either support or oppose the implementation of CSE (Chanda, 2023). In many cases, cultural beliefs may promote conservative views on sexuality, favoring abstinence and limited discussion on sexual health. Similarly, religious beliefs play a significant role, as many religious groups have specific doctrines regarding sexual behavior, morality, and education. These beliefs can influence parental attitudes and the broader community's acceptance of CSE, sometimes leading to resistance based on the perception that CSE contradicts or undermines religious teachings. However, there can also be opportunities for alignment when CSE is framed in a way that respects and incorporates these cultural and religious values, promoting a holistic understanding of sexual health that is consistent with the community's beliefs.

Barriers to the implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) encompass a range of obstacles that hinder the effective delivery and acceptance of CSE programs. These barriers can be categorized into societal, cultural, religious, and institutional challenges. Societal barriers include a lack of awareness and understanding of the importance and benefits of CSE, which can lead to resistance from communities and policymakers (Browes, 2015). Cultural barriers often involve deeply ingrained cultural norms and practices that may oppose the content or delivery methods of CSE, such as views on discussing sexual health openly. Religious barriers can arise when religious beliefs and doctrines conflict with the principles of CSE, leading to opposition from religious groups or institutions. Ailyn (2012) added that institutional barriers include inadequate training for educators, insufficient resources, and lack of support from educational authorities, which can impede the effective implementation of CSE. Addressing these barriers requires a multi-faceted approach that involves engaging communities, aligning CSE with cultural and religious contexts, and strengthening institutional support and resources.

1.2 Statement of the problem

In Zambian schools, the implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) faces significant challenges due to varying parental attitudes influenced by cultural and religious beliefs. Many parents perceive CSE as a sensitive topic that conflicts with traditional values and norms, leading to resistance and apprehension regarding its inclusion in the school curriculum (Munsaka & Mwape, 2020). This resistance is often rooted in fears about promoting early sexual activity or undermining traditional moral teachings. However, there are also opportunities for successful implementation if these barriers are addressed. Kasonde (2013)'s study elucidated that engaging with parents through community outreach, educational workshops, and inclusive dialogues can help demystify CSE and demonstrate its benefits for improving adolescent health and well-being. By aligning CSE with cultural values and emphasizing its role in equipping students with essential knowledge, educators and policymakers can work towards overcoming resistance and fostering a more supportive environment for comprehensive sexual education in Zambian schools.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of studying the ethical implications of AI and machine learning in education was to explore and address the potential risks and ethical dilemmas these technologies present in educational settings.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

- To examine the impact of parental attitudes towards comprehensive sexuality education within Zambian schools.
- To identify barriers and opportunities for effective implementation of comprehensive sexuality education within Zambian schools.

1.5 Conceptual Framework

In exploring parental attitudes towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools, the conceptual framework centers on understanding the interplay between cultural, religious, and socio-economic factors and their influence on the acceptance and implementation of CSE programs. This framework considers parental attitudes as pivotal in shaping educational policies and practices related to sexuality education (Mumtazah et al, 2024). Cultural beliefs and religious values often play a significant role in forming these attitudes, potentially leading to resistance or support for CSE. Additionally, socio-economic factors such as access to resources and educational background influence how parents perceive the necessity and appropriateness of CSE. The framework also highlights opportunities for overcoming barriers, such as community engagement initiatives, awareness campaigns, and educational reforms that address cultural and religious sensitivities while promoting the benefits of CSE (Smith, 2000). By integrating these elements, the framework aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors affecting parental attitudes and identify strategies to enhance the successful implementation of CSE in Zambian schools.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The significance of the study on parental attitudes towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools lies in its potential to address critical barriers and identify opportunities for effective implementation. Understanding parental attitudes is crucial as these perceptions significantly influence the acceptance and integration of CSE programs within educational institutions. By exploring the barriers parents face, such as cultural and religious beliefs, misinformation, or perceived irrelevance, the study aims to uncover the challenges that hinder the successful delivery of CSE. Simultaneously, identifying opportunities for implementation, including educational campaigns, community engagement, and policy support, can help in developing strategies that align with parental concerns and cultural values. This research not only contributes to enhancing the quality and reach of CSE but also fosters a more inclusive approach that respects local contexts while addressing the educational needs of students regarding sexual health and well-being.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a mixed methods approach which is a combination of quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive understanding (Banda et al, 2017). The study was conducted in 6 selected schools; 3 secondary and 3 primary schools within Lusaka district in Zambia. The sample consisted 200 respondents; 10% of the target population 2000. The population

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for the study was purposefully drawn from the 6 schools. Purposive sampling procedure was used to select head teachers (6); 1 representing each school, and teachers (18); 3 representing each school, while simple random sampling procedure was used to select the pupils (150); 25 representing each school, and 26 parents. Structured open-ended interviews, focus groups and questionnaires were used to respondents to collect data. The quantitative data collected through the questionnaires were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) and Microsoft excel whereas the qualitative data from semi structured interviews and focus groups were analyzed thematically. The study upheld research ethical considerations such as voluntary participation of the respondents, informed consent, confidentiality, honesty, and right of privacy.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Impact of Parental Attitudes towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education

According to research findings, the impact of parental attitudes towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) within Zambian schools is significant, as these attitudes can either support or hinder the successful implementation of CSE programs. Hence, the study identified five main factors with regards to the impact of parental attitudes towards CSE in schools. Student Engagement and Learning was at 35%, Barriers to Implementation at 25%, Influence on Curriculum Implementation at 15%, Teacher Preparedness and Confidence at 15%, and Policy and School Administration Decisions at 10%. Findings were summarized in figure1.

The study results noted that parental attitudes towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools significantly impact student engagement and learning. When parents hold positive views towards CSE, students are more likely to engage actively in these programs, resulting in enhanced understanding of sexual health, responsible decision-making, and improved academic performance. Supportive parental attitudes create an environment where students feel comfortable discussing sensitive topics, fostering open communication both at home and in school (Achen et al, 2023). Conversely, negative parental attitudes can lead to student disengagement, as students may feel conflicted or stigmatized, which can hinder their learning and understanding of crucial sexual health information. Chavula et al (2022a) says that this resistance may also result in students developing misconceptions or lacking vital knowledge, ultimately affecting their overall educational outcomes and personal development. Therefore, parental attitudes play a critical role in shaping the effectiveness of CSE in promoting student engagement and learning in Zambian schools.

The study results also showed that the implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools faces significant barriers due to prevailing parental attitudes. Many parents in Zambia harbor strong reservations towards CSE, often perceiving it as inappropriate for children or conflicting with cultural and religious values. Chanda & Chitondo (2023) says that culture is the complex and broad set of relationships, values, attitudes, and behaviors that bind a specific community consciously and unconsciously. This skepticism stems from concerns that CSE may encourage promiscuity or challenge traditional norms, leading to resistance against its integration into the school curriculum. Additionally, there is a lack of understanding among parents

about the objectives and benefits of CSE, further fueling their opposition. This resistance creates a challenging environment for educators and policymakers, making it difficult to implement CSE effectively. Eleanor (2019) supported this finding by stating that the absence of parental support not only hampers the adoption of CSE programs but also limits the resources and community involvement necessary for their successful execution, ultimately hindering efforts to provide students with the essential knowledge and skills to make informed decisions about their sexual and reproductive health.

Teachers explained that parental attitudes towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools significantly influence curriculum implementation. These attitudes, often shaped by cultural, religious, and social beliefs, can either support or hinder the successful integration of CSE into the educational system. One of the teachers alluded that:

“Parental attitudes, whether supportive or resistant, directly affect how CSE is introduced and maintained within schools. Positive attitudes can lead to more open communication between parents, educators, and students, ensuring that CSE is integrated effectively”.

Gisa (2020)’s study noted that parents who view CSE as essential for their children's development tend to advocate for its thorough implementation, thereby encouraging schools to adopt and teach the curriculum effectively. Conversely, parents who oppose CSE, believing it conflicts with their values, may resist its introduction or request that their children be exempted from such lessons, leading to selective implementation or even the omission of key components of the curriculum. This resistance can pressure educational authorities to modify or dilute the content to avoid conflict, ultimately affecting the comprehensiveness and effectiveness of the CSE curriculum. Therefore, parental attitudes play a critical role in shaping how CSE is delivered in Zambian schools, impacting the overall success of the program and its ability to meet educational goals (Chanda et al, 2024).

Head teachers also observed that teacher preparedness and confidence in delivering Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools are significantly influenced by parental attitudes. When parents hold positive or supportive views toward CSE, teachers are more likely to feel confident and adequately prepared to teach the subject, as they perceive a cooperative and encouraging environment that aligns with educational goals. Conversely, when parents express negative attitudes or opposition to CSE, teachers may face increased anxiety, hesitation, and a lack of confidence in delivering the curriculum. This resistance can stem from fear of backlash or criticism from parents, leading to insufficient preparation and a reluctance to fully engage with the subject matter (Cooper & Schindler, 2008). In some cases, negative parental attitudes may result in teachers avoiding certain topics altogether, further compromising the effectiveness of CSE in schools. Therefore, the level of teacher preparedness and confidence is closely tied to the broader social and parental support for CSE, making it crucial for educators to work alongside parents to foster a positive and collaborative approach to sexuality education.

The findings further noted that parental attitudes towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) significantly influence policy and school administration decisions in Zambian schools. In communities where parents strongly oppose CSE due to cultural or religious beliefs, schools may face pressure to limit or modify the curriculum, resulting in the exclusion of critical topics related to sexual health and rights (Chanda, 2023b). This resistance can lead to a cautious approach in

policy formulation, where educational authorities may opt to downplay or altogether omit comprehensive aspects of sexuality education to avoid conflicts with parents and local communities. Consequently, school administrators may prioritize aligning with parental preferences over adhering to international or national guidelines on CSE, thereby affecting the overall effectiveness and reach of such programs. Additionally, in some cases, schools might implement opt-out policies, allowing parents to exclude their children from CSE classes, which further undermines the uniformity and comprehensiveness of the education provided (Diiorio et al, 2003). This dynamic illustrates the complex interplay between parental attitudes and the administrative and policy decisions that shape the delivery of CSE in Zambian schools.

Figure1: Impact of Parental Attitudes towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education

3.2. Barriers and Opportunities for Effective Implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education in Zambian Schools

3.2.1. Barriers for Effective Implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education

The findings showed that limited resources and materials present a significant barrier to the effective implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools. Many educational institutions, particularly those in rural and underfunded areas, struggle with a shortage of essential resources such as textbooks, teaching aids, and multimedia tools tailored to teach effectively (Chanda et al, 2024b). This scarcity hinders educators' ability to deliver comprehensive, accurate, and engaging lessons on sexuality education. Additionally, the lack of culturally appropriate and locally relevant materials further complicates the situation, as existing resources may not fully address the specific needs and concerns of Zambian students. The

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insufficient allocation of funds for teacher training also exacerbates this issue, as educators are often not equipped with the necessary skills or materials to effectively teach CSE (Chandra-Mouli et al, 2018). Consequently, students may receive inconsistent or incomplete information, undermining the overall goals of CSE in promoting informed and healthy choices regarding sexuality and relationships.

Furthermore, socio-economic challenges significantly impact the effective implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambia, creating substantial barriers that hinder its success. In many communities, economic hardship leads to a lack of resources and infrastructure necessary for delivering CSE programs. Chanda et al, (2024c)'s study added that schools in low-income areas often struggle with inadequate facilities, insufficient educational materials, and a shortage of trained teachers, all of which undermine the quality of education obtained. Additionally, poverty and economic instability may compel families to prioritize immediate financial needs over educational investments, resulting in reduced support for CSE programs and limited parental involvement. Socio-economic disparities can also exacerbate issues of access and equity, where students from poorer backgrounds may not benefit equally from CSE due to fewer opportunities for participation and support. Moreover, economic pressures can lead to high rates of absenteeism and dropouts, further impacting the continuity and effectiveness of CSE. Chanda (2023c) says a dropout is a pupil who was enrolled in the beginning of the school year and has left before the end of the school year, and was not enrolled elsewhere. Addressing these socio-economic barriers requires a multifaceted approach that includes increasing funding for educational resources, improving infrastructure, and implementing community-based support systems to ensure that all students have access to comprehensive and effective sexuality education (Bruce, 2001).

Parents explained that cultural and religious resistance poses a significant barrier to the effective implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in many contexts, including Zambian schools. This resistance often stems from deeply ingrained cultural norms and religious beliefs that prioritize traditional values over modern educational approaches (Chanda, 2023d). One of the parents pointed out that:

“Cultural norms and religious beliefs often conflict with the content and objectives of CSE, leading to opposition from parents, community leaders, and religious institutions. Many believe that discussing sexual matters openly is inappropriate, especially with young people”.

In various communities, sexuality is considered a taboo subject, and discussing it openly can be seen as challenging established norms. Cultural attitudes may view CSE as conflicting with traditional practices and moral values, leading to resistance from parents, community leaders, and even educators. Religious beliefs can further complicate this issue, as certain faith-based perspectives may emphasize abstinence or restrict discussions on sexual health, which can undermine the inclusivity and comprehensiveness of CSE programs. This resistance not only affects the acceptance of CSE but also impacts the quality and reach of education provided, as educators may be hesitant to cover essential topics or adapt curricula to align with conservative expectations (Dancil, 2002). Consequently, addressing these cultural and religious barriers is crucial for the successful implementation of CSE, requiring a sensitive and inclusive approach that respects local values while promoting the importance of sexual health and rights.

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Furthermore, parental attitudes and misconceptions significantly hinder the effective implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools. Many parents harbor deep-seated beliefs that frame sexuality education as inappropriate or harmful, often due to cultural and religious influences. These misconceptions include the fear that CSE will encourage sexual activity among youth, undermine traditional values, or infringe on parental authority (UNESCO, 2018). Such attitudes can lead to resistance against school programs and reluctance to support CSE initiatives. Furthermore, misconceptions about the content and goals of CSE contribute to misunderstandings, making it challenging for educators to communicate the program's benefits and relevance. To overcome these barriers, it is crucial to engage parents through educational campaigns that address their concerns, highlight the evidence-based benefits of CSE, and emphasize the alignment of CSE with cultural and ethical values (Zagat, 2012). By fostering a supportive dialogue and involving parents in the educational process, schools can create a more conducive environment for the successful implementation of CSE programs.

The study also revealed that inadequate policy support is a significant barrier to the effective implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in many educational systems, including those in Zambia. UNESCO (2012)'s report explained that without a robust policy framework, CSE programs often lack the necessary guidance and structure to be successfully integrated into the curriculum. Policies that are vague, inconsistent, or absent can result in fragmented and uneven delivery of CSE, with varying levels of quality and effectiveness across different schools and regions. Additionally, insufficient policy support can lead to a lack of standardized training for educators, impeding their ability to deliver the curriculum confidently and competently. The absence of clear policies also undermines the allocation of adequate resources and funding for CSE programs, further diminishing their impact (UN, 2007). Furthermore, inadequate policy support may contribute to resistance from stakeholders who are not adequately informed or engaged, thus exacerbating challenges related to cultural and religious opposition. The lack of strong, well-defined policy support hampers the successful implementation of CSE by creating an environment where the curriculum is inconsistently applied, inadequately resourced, and poorly supported, ultimately affecting the educational outcomes and the well-being of students.

Additionally, the implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in schools often faces significant barriers due to the fear of controversy and backlash. Educators, administrators, and policymakers may hesitate to adopt CSE programs because of concerns about negative reactions from parents, community members, or religious groups. Chanda (2024) says that this apprehension is driven by the potential for public outcry, accusations of promoting inappropriate content, or undermining traditional values and beliefs. One of the head teachers noted that:

“Schools and educators may avoid fully engaging with CSE due to fears of backlash from parents, communities, or authorities. This can lead to a watered-down version of CSE that does not meet educational objectives”.

In many communities, discussions about sexuality are deeply intertwined with cultural and religious norms, making any deviation from these norms contentious. As a result, stakeholders may prioritize avoiding conflict over providing students with crucial, age-appropriate sexual health education. This fear can lead to watered-down curricula, inadequate training for educators, and

limited resources, all of which undermine the effectiveness of teaching programs (Mpolomoka et al, 2017). Moreover, the backlash can foster a climate of censorship and reluctance to address important topics related to sexual health, further perpetuating misinformation and reducing the overall impact of educational efforts. To overcome these challenges, it is essential to engage in open dialogue with stakeholders, provide clear evidence of the benefits of CSE, and ensure that educational materials are sensitive to cultural contexts while still delivering comprehensive information (Malunga et al, 2023).

Moving on, inconsistent curriculum integration also poses a significant barrier to the effective implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in schools. The respondents stated that the lack of a standardized, coherent approach often results in fragmented and uneven delivery of CSE content, leading to gaps in students' knowledge and understanding. UNFPA (2012) noted that in many instances, CSE is not fully embedded into the overall curriculum but is treated as an add-on or supplementary topic, which can undermine its importance and effectiveness. This inconsistency can be attributed to various factors, including differences in educational policies, varying levels of support from school administrations, and the absence of a clear, unified framework guiding CSE implementation. Furthermore, teachers may face challenges in delivering CSE content consistently due to limited resources, inadequate training, and a lack of comprehensive guidelines. As a result, students may receive varying levels of CSE, depending on their school's approach, which can affect their overall learning experience and the program's impact. This was in line with (Chanda, 2024b) who said that adequate funding ensures that schools can offer a diverse range of educational programs, extracurricular activities, and necessary resources such as textbooks and technology. Addressing this issue requires a more integrated and systemic approach to curriculum design, where CSE is seamlessly incorporated into the broader educational framework, supported by clear guidelines, adequate teacher training, and consistent evaluation mechanisms to ensure effective and equitable delivery across all schools.

Figure2: Barriers for Effective Implementation of CSE

3.2.2. Opportunities for Effective Implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education

The study results showed that engaging stakeholders is crucial for the effective implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in schools. This involves actively involving a diverse group of participants including parents, educators, community leaders, health professionals, and policymakers to foster a supportive environment for CSE. By involving these stakeholders, educational institutions can ensure that the curriculum is culturally and contextually relevant, addressing the specific needs and concerns of the community (Daniel, 2000). Stakeholder engagement facilitates the sharing of knowledge and resources, which can enhance the quality and acceptance of CSE programs. Parents, for example, can provide valuable insights into cultural norms and values that may influence the design and delivery of CSE, while educators and health professionals can offer expertise on effective teaching methods and health issues. Furthermore, involving policymakers can help in securing necessary funding and support for CSE initiatives. Chanda (2024d) alluded that building a collaborative approach with stakeholders not only promotes a more inclusive and comprehensive educational framework but also helps in addressing potential resistance and barriers to implementation. Overall, effective stakeholder engagement leads to a more holistic and sustainable approach to delivering CSE, ultimately contributing to its success and impact in promoting sexual health and well-being among students.

Additionally, training and professional development play a crucial role in the effective implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in schools. These opportunities equip educators with the necessary knowledge, skills, and confidence to deliver CSE content effectively and sensitively. One of the head teachers expressed that:

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“Training programs can provide teachers with updated information on sexual and reproductive health, pedagogical strategies tailored to different age groups, and techniques for creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment”.

Professional development also fosters continuous learning and adaptation to emerging issues in sexuality education, ensuring that educators remain informed about best practices and legal requirements. (Mpolomoka et al, 2023)’s study showed that by participating in specialized workshops, seminars, and ongoing education, teachers can overcome challenges related to misinformation, cultural resistance, and personal discomfort. Furthermore, professional development helps build a network of support among educators, allowing for the exchange of experiences and strategies (Lufupa et al, 2024). This comprehensive approach not only enhances teachers' effectiveness but also contributes to the overall success of CSE programs by creating a more informed and responsive educational environment.

Furthermore, the study noted that creating a safe learning environment is essential for the effective implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in schools. A safe learning environment fosters open communication, mutual respect, and emotional security, which are crucial for students to engage with sensitive topics like sexual health and relationships. This environment should be free from discrimination, harassment, and bullying, allowing students to explore and discuss CSE topics without fear of judgment or reprisal (Chanda, 2023e). It involves establishing clear policies and practices that promote inclusivity and respect for diverse perspectives and experiences. Teachers and school staff must be trained to handle CSE topics with sensitivity and to support students' emotional well-being. Moreover, involving parents and guardians in the development and implementation of CSE programs can help address cultural and religious concerns, ensuring that the education provided is respectful and relevant to the community. By creating a supportive and non-judgmental atmosphere, schools can enhance students' willingness to participate in CSE, leading to more effective learning outcomes and healthier attitudes towards sexuality and relationships (Kaduyu & Musagazi, 2022).

Moving on, the results indicated that leveraging technology presents significant opportunities for the effective implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE). The integration of digital tools can enhance the reach and accessibility of CSE programs, overcoming geographical and logistical barriers that often impede traditional methods. Online platforms, such as e-learning modules and interactive applications, allow for flexible and personalized learning experiences, catering to diverse needs and learning styles (Chanda et al, 2024e). Virtual simulations and multimedia resources can make complex concepts more engaging and easier to understand, fostering better comprehension and retention. Additionally, technology enables the development of confidential and safe spaces for students to explore sensitive topics, ask questions anonymously, and receive accurate information. Mobile apps and online forums can also facilitate continuous support and dialogue, bridging gaps between formal education and real-life application (UNFPA, 2019). By incorporating data analytics, educators can monitor progress, identify gaps, and tailor content to address specific challenges. However, successful implementation requires addressing digital divides, ensuring equitable access to technology, and providing adequate training for educators to effectively utilize these tools. Overall, Chanda & Zohaib (2024)’s findings indicated

that harnessing technology in education can lead to more inclusive, interactive, and impactful educational experiences.

The study also revealed that utilizing evidence-based materials presents a significant opportunity for the effective implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools. Teachers alluded that evidence-based materials, derived from rigorous research and best practices, ensure that the content delivered is both accurate and relevant to the students' needs. These materials can include updated curricula, teaching guides, and multimedia resources that address key areas such as sexual health, consent, and respectful relationships (Fisseha et al, 2017). By integrating evidence-based materials into CSE programs, educators can provide students with the most current and effective information, leading to a more informed and engaged learning experience. Additionally, these materials can help bridge gaps in knowledge and correct misconceptions, promoting a more comprehensive understanding of sexuality and health. This approach also supports the development of critical thinking and decision-making skills among students, empowering them to make informed choices about their health and relationships. Moreover, evidence-based materials can assist in aligning CSE programs with national and international standards, enhancing their credibility and acceptance among stakeholders, including parents and policymakers (Haberland, 2015). Ultimately, leveraging evidence-based resources contributes to the overall success and sustainability of CSE initiatives, fostering a healthier and more informed generation.

Further, addressing cultural and religious concerns represents a significant opportunity for the effective implementation of Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools. Cultural and religious beliefs heavily influence societal attitudes toward sexuality education, often resulting in resistance to such programs. By engaging with community leaders, educators, and parents to understand and respect these beliefs, CSE programs can be tailored to align with cultural values while still delivering essential information. This approach fosters a more supportive environment for CSE, encouraging acceptance and participation from both students and their families (Kapungwe, 2003). Respondents also explained that incorporating culturally sensitive materials and approaches into the curriculum can help bridge gaps and address misconceptions, making the education more relevant and acceptable.

Additionally, providing training for teachers to handle sensitive topics with cultural and religious sensitivity ensures that they can effectively address concerns and foster a safe learning environment. Collaboration with local cultural and religious organizations can also facilitate open dialogue and address any resistance, ultimately enhancing the program's effectiveness and sustainability. Zohaib et al (2024) in their study, they noted that education for sustainable development (ESD) emphasizes the crucial role of educational institutions in tackling social, economic, and environmental problems through their curricula. Engaging parents and community members fosters a supportive environment that enhances the acceptability and success of CSE programs. When parents are actively involved, they can contribute to shaping the curriculum, ensuring it aligns with cultural values while addressing essential topics. Pupils expressed that community involvement helps to address misconceptions and biases about CSE, promoting a more inclusive and informed approach. Collaboration between educators, parents, and community leaders can facilitate better resource allocation and support, creating a holistic educational

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experience (Chanda et al, 2024f). By fostering open communication and building partnerships, CSE programs can gain broader community support, which is essential for overcoming resistance and ensuring that students receive accurate and comprehensive information about sexuality and reproductive health. This collective effort not only improves the quality and relevance of the education provided but also empowers families and communities to play an active role in the well-being and development of young people (Chanda, 2024a).

4. CONCLUSION

Parental attitudes towards Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) in Zambian schools reveal a complex interplay of barriers and opportunities influencing its implementation. While many parents recognize the importance of CSE in addressing critical issues such as sexual health and well-being, cultural and religious beliefs often present significant obstacles. These beliefs can lead to resistance against CSE, with concerns about its content contradicting traditional values or promoting behaviors seen as inappropriate. Additionally, a lack of awareness about the benefits of CSE and insufficient communication between schools and parents contribute to misunderstandings and reluctance. However, opportunities for effective implementation exist through community engagement, educational campaigns, and inclusive dialogues that address these concerns. By fostering a collaborative approach that respects cultural values while highlighting the educational and health benefits of CSE, stakeholders can overcome resistance and enhance the program's acceptance and impact.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study;

1. Enhanced Community Engagement and Education:

- Schools should develop and implement community-based educational programs and workshops to inform and engage parents about the benefits and goals of CSE. These programs should address common misconceptions, highlight the positive impacts of CSE on students' well-being and academic success, and provide a platform for parents to ask questions and express concerns.

2. Inclusive Policy Development and Consultation:

- Curriculum developers should involve parents and community leaders in the development and review of CSE policies and curricula. Establish advisory committees or focus groups that include diverse parental perspectives to ensure that the content is culturally and contextually appropriate.

3. Professional Development and Support for Educators:

- Government through teacher training institutions should provide teachers with specialized training and resources to effectively deliver CSE and manage parental concerns. This training should include strategies for communicating with parents, handling sensitive topics, and addressing resistance or backlash constructively.

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